

A bond-level energy-based peridynamics for mixed-mode fracture in rocks

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Abstract

This paper deals with the numerical simulation of initiation and propagation of mixed mode fracture in rocks. A bond-level energy-based peridynamic model is developed by introducing a dilatation function to capture both volumetric and deviatoric deformations. We proceed to define the nonlocal stresses to obtain the isotropic and deviatoric forces commensurate with the deformations. We then come up with a new failure model to link computational peridynamics with some phenomenological failure criteria, which is highly relevant for both brittle and quasi-brittle rocks. Finally, several numerical examples of mixed-mode fractures are presented to show the performance of our model.

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Keywords: Ordinary state-based peridynamics; Nonlocal stress tensor; Energy-based failure criteria; Mixed-mode fracture; Rock materials

1. Introduction

Over the last decades, rock fracture mechanics remains a challenging research subject [1–7] and has become an essential tool for the design practice in rock engineering [8,9]. Moreover, rock fracture often serves as the precursory for geohazards, such as earthquakes [10], rock avalanches [11], and volcanic eruptions [12], and play an important role in assessing the stability and safety of rock engineering facilities, like deep geological disposal of nuclear waste [13], deep geothermal exploitation [14], and deep mining excavation [15].

Rock fracture can be studied either by experimental or numerical approaches. Field and laboratory experiments are usually limited by measurement accuracy, costs and time. As a result, the quantification of deformation and evolution of fracture networks in rock masses remains difficult and challenging. On the other hand, numerical analysis can provide deep insights into rock fracture mechanism, such as full-field deformation, internal fracture networks, energy evolution and dissipation, which plays an important role in the modern geomechanics. Over the past decades, some mesh-based methods (e.g., FEM, XFEM [16]) and mesh-free methods (e.g., DEM [17], SPH [18]) have been developed to simulate rock fracture process, including crack initiation, propagation, and coalescence. These numerical methods are based on the classical local continuum mechanics [6,19–21], with their inherent drawbacks to address fracture problems. For instance, FEM requires the remeshing techniques to model crack initiation and propagation. XFEM is known to have some difficulties in dealing with multiple crack

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propagation and three-dimensional crack topological calculation. As to DEM, the calibration procedure of the microscopic parameters in DEM simulations is often dependent on some empirical relationships. For SPH, the Neumann boundary conditions are difficult to handle.

Peridynamic (PD) theory was proposed based on the nonlocal continuum mechanics for discontinuities, where the PDEs of motion are reformulated by the integral-differential equations without any spatial derivatives of displacements [22]. Peridynamics possesses some advantages, which allow for the spontaneous initiation and propagation of cracks without resort to the bifurcation criteria [23,24]. These advantages make the computational peridynamics appealing for various engineering applications [25–38]. For more application areas, the readers are referred to some review articles [39–41] and books [42,43]. To date, PD models are classified into three categories, i.e., bond-based (BB), ordinary state-based (OSB), and non-ordinary state-based (NOSB) [44,45]. The bond-based peridynamic (BB-PD) model employs the pairwise force density between two points and ignores the deformation of other bonds within one *horizon*, resulting in the fixed Poisson's ratio. To circumvent this dilemma, SB-PD was developed using force vector and deformation scalar states, which allows for convenient implementation of classical local constitutive relations. In NOSB-PD, due to the direct approximation of deformation gradients, zero-energy deformation mode may result in some unstable solutions [46,47]. Although some specific numerical treatments [48–50] have been proposed to suppress its occurrence, the negative effects on the stable solution still remain. Compared with NOSB-PD, no numerical instabilities are observed in OSB-PD simulations, because the bond-level kinematic and mechanical variables are maintained all along.

The bond-breakage failure criterion is pivotal for computational peridynamics. By building the relationship between critical bond stretch/stored bond energy density and the critical fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_c , the tensile-dominated fracture can be simulated fairly well. While, the shear-dominated fracture and mixed-mode fracture are rarely simulated by peridynamics. To address the mixed-mode fracture properly, some efforts were made to develop SB-PD models for the cases with $\mathcal{G}_{IIc} \neq \mathcal{G}_{Ic}$. Wang et al. [51] proposed stress-based failure criteria in NOSB-PD to simulate the mixed-mode fracture, which was then extended to anisotropic shale [27]. The hybrid bond failure criteria, including critical bond stretch and stored bond energy density, were developed in the conjugated bond-pair-based peridynamics [52] to simulate mixed-mode fracture of brittle rocks in 2-D [53] and 3-D [54]. Yu's group [55,56] proposed a unified nonlocal model bridging the gap between local and nonlocal methods, which shows great advantages for more complex discontinuous problems, including rate-dependent, multi-scale, multi-physical and mix-mode fracture behaviors of quasi-brittle solids [57,58]. Wang et al. [59] proposed an extended peridynamic model, where the bond stretch is combined with the dilatational potential, for simulating mixed-mode rock fracture. Yang et al. [60] proposed a method for the peridynamics-based cohesive zone to handle quasi-brittle failure. Zhang et al. [61] reported on the critical skew criterion within OSB-PD framework for the mode-II fracture analysis in composite materials, which was then extended to the mixed-mode fracture analysis [62]. However, these studies are concerned mainly with the cases where $\mathcal{G}_{IIc} \approx \mathcal{G}_{Ic}$ or $\mathcal{G}_{IIc} < \mathcal{G}_{Ic}$ in composite materials.

Despite these efforts, however, a mixed-mode bond-breakage PD model for the realistic rock masses with $\mathcal{G}_{IIc} > \mathcal{G}_{Ic}$ is not yet available. Moreover, most models assume that the critical fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_c remains constant, independent on the fracture modes. Obviously, the existing PD models are not capable of addressing the compressive-shear mixed-mode fracture in rock masses. In this work, we propose a new bond-level energy-based PD model to simulate the mixed-mode fracture behavior of rocks under compression or mixed shear-compression. The criterion for tensile/compressive-shear mixed-mode of our proposed numerical model can be expressed by a unified formula, where the pure mode-I and mode-II cracks are recovered as special cases. Overall, our paper contains the following innovative aspects:

- A new dilatation scalar function is formulated to describe the volumetric and deviatoric parts of mechanical deformation.
- The hydrostatic stress state is redefined to decompose force state into the isotropic part and the deviatoric one.
- A new bond-level energy-based failure criterion is proposed to simulate mixed-mode compressive/tensile-shear fracture behaviors by linking with the specific failure criteria.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 derives the formulations of OSB-PD. Section 3 provides the novel bond-level energy-based failure criterion. Section 4 describes the numerical solution strategy. Section 5 solves the benchmark problems for numerical validation. Section 6 shows numerical simulations of crack propagation and coalescence in rock materials. Finally, Section 7 presents the conclusions from this work.

Fig. 1. (a) Nonlocal continuum computational domain Ω bounded by $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_t \cup \mathcal{S}_u$ for the brittle rock materials, and (b) partition of the interaction for mechanical equilibrium.

2. Peridynamic formulations

2.1. Kinematic and deformation states

Ordinary state-based peridynamics (OSB-PD) proposed by Silling [44,45] is one kind of integral-type nonlocal continuum models [63], where the integral with respect to the displacement \mathbf{u} . We consider the arbitrary solid domain $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$, where n denotes the spatial dimension, in the reference configuration bounded by \mathcal{S} , as shown in Fig. 1(a). We denote \mathbf{n} as the outward unit normal to \mathcal{S} , which is composed of displacement-prescribed boundary \mathcal{S}_u and the traction-prescribed boundary \mathcal{S}_t , satisfying $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_u \cup \mathcal{S}_t$ and $\mathcal{S}_u \cap \mathcal{S}_t = \emptyset$. It assumes that any material point \mathbf{x} interacts with all the points \mathbf{x}' in its neighborhood region $\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}$, in which δ is a horizon that denotes the cut-off radius similar to bond-based peridynamics [22]. In OSB-PD, the concept of *state* is introduced to describe the kinematic compatibility and momentum equilibrium among material points within one $\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}$, as shown in Fig. 1(b).

To describe the material point position within $\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}$, the *bond vector state* in the reference configuration is expressed as

$$\underline{\mathbf{X}}(\xi) = \xi = \mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

where ξ is the relative position vector between material points \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' in the reference configuration, and the relevant *bond scalar state* is

$$\underline{x}(\xi) = \|\underline{\mathbf{X}}(\xi)\| = \|\xi\| \quad (2)$$

Similarly, the *deformation vector state field* is defined to describe the position of material point $\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in the deformed configuration as

$$\underline{\mathbf{Y}}(\xi) = \mathbf{y}'(\mathbf{x}, t) - \mathbf{y}(\mathbf{x}, t) = (\mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{u}') - (\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{u}) = \xi + \eta \quad (3)$$

in which $\eta = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}', t) - \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ denotes the relative displacement vector between material points \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{y}' in the deformed configuration, and the associated *deformation scalar state* is

$$\underline{y}(\xi) = \|\underline{\mathbf{Y}}(\xi)\| = \|\xi + \eta\| \quad (4)$$

The extension scalar state of one bond ξ between two interacting material points \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' in the deformed configuration is described as

$$\underline{e}(\xi) = \underline{y} - \underline{x} = \|\xi + \eta\| - \|\xi\| \quad (5)$$

As defined by Silling [44,45], a scalar-valued dilatation function $\theta(\underline{e})$ is directly equal to the change in volume over the neighboring material points of \mathbf{x} , i.e., $\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}$

$$\theta(\underline{e}) = \frac{3}{m} (\underline{\omega x}) \bullet \underline{e} = \frac{3}{m} \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}} \omega(\|\xi\|) \|\xi\| \cdot \underline{e}(\xi) dV_{x'} \quad \text{for 3-D} \quad (6a)$$

Fig. 2. Kinematic decomposition of volumetric and deviatoric deformation between two interacting material points within one horizon.

$$\theta(\underline{e}) = \frac{2}{m} (\underline{\omega x}) \bullet \underline{e} = \frac{2}{m} \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}} \omega(\|\xi\|) \|\xi\| \cdot \underline{e}(\xi) dV_{x'} \quad \text{for 2-D} \quad (6b)$$

in which $\underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|)$ denotes the *influence function state* for weighting the contribution of each bond ξ within $\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}$, and m is the scalar-valued weighted volumetric factor defined as [44,64]

$$m = (\underline{\omega x}) \bullet \underline{x} = \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}} \omega(\|\xi\|) \|\xi\|^2 dV_{x'} \quad (7)$$

In the previous state-based peridynamics, the volumetric dilatation function can be estimated by the total extension scalar state [44,45] and the displacement state $\underline{U}[x, t](\xi)$ [65]. While, the extensional part and displacement component caused by the distortion may be involved in these two kinds of approximations. In this work, we suppose that the extension scalar state of one bond can be approximate divided into two parts: the pure dilatation part (along the direction of ξ) and the pure distortion one (perpendicular to the direction of ξ), as shown in Fig. 2. The new dilatation scalar-valued functions in 3-D and 2-D cases are defined in the following expressions, respectively.

$$\theta(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta)) = \frac{3}{m} (\underline{\omega x}) \bullet \underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta) = \frac{3}{m} \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}} \omega(\|\xi\|) \|\xi\| \cdot \underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta) dV_{x'} \quad \text{for 3-D} \quad (8a)$$

$$\theta(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta)) = \frac{2}{m} (\underline{\omega x}) \bullet \underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta) = \frac{2}{m} \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}} \omega(\|\xi\|) \|\xi\| \cdot \underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta) dV_{x'} \quad \text{for 2-D} \quad (8b)$$

where $\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta)$ is the *normal extension scalar state*, which is geometrically approximated as

$$\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta) = \underline{y}(\xi) \cos \varphi - \underline{x}(\xi) = \|\xi + \eta\| \cos \varphi - \|\xi\| \quad (9)$$

in which φ represents the angle between the initial bond ξ and the deformed bond $\xi + \eta$.

Moreover, ignoring the high-order term in Taylor expansion of Eq. (9), the normal extension scalar state yields

$$\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta) \approx \underline{U}_n \hat{\underline{M}}(\xi) \quad (10)$$

where $\underline{U}_n = \eta_n$ denotes the normal component of relative displacement vector, and $\hat{\underline{M}}(\xi) = \frac{\xi}{\|\xi\|}$ represents the direction state of one given bond ξ , as shown in Fig. 2.

2.2. Governing equations

The governing equation of motion at the material point x is expressed in the following integral-differential form [44].

$$\rho(x) \ddot{\underline{u}}(x, t) = \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta(x)}} \{ \underline{T}[x, t](\xi) - \underline{T}[x', t](\xi) \} dV_{x'} + \underline{b}(x, t) \quad (11)$$

where ρ is the mass density, $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$ denotes the acceleration vector field, $\underline{\mathbf{T}}$ is the force vector state and \mathbf{b} represents the body force density. Furthermore, the integrand $\{\underline{\mathbf{T}}[\mathbf{x}, t] \langle \xi \rangle - \underline{\mathbf{T}}[\mathbf{x}', t] \langle -\xi \rangle\}$ represents the force density exerting on the material point \mathbf{x} by the interacting material point \mathbf{x}' within $\mathcal{H}_{\delta(\mathbf{x})}$.

In the framework of ordinary state-based peridynamics, the force vector state is

$$\underline{\mathbf{T}}[\mathbf{x}, t] \langle \xi \rangle = \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{\mathbf{M}}(\xi) \tag{12}$$

in which $\underline{t}(\xi)$ represents the scalar force state field, and $\underline{\mathbf{M}}(\xi)$ denotes the direction of the deformed bond as [44]

$$\underline{\mathbf{M}}(\underline{\mathbf{Y}}) \langle \xi \rangle = \frac{\underline{\mathbf{Y}}}{\|\underline{\mathbf{Y}}\|} = \frac{\xi + \eta}{\|\xi + \eta\|} \tag{13}$$

The macro-elastic strain energy density $\mathcal{W}^p(\theta(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta)), \underline{e}^d)$ for the ordinary elastic peridynamic solids can be rewritten by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}^p(\theta(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta)), \underline{e}^d) &= \frac{\kappa}{2} \theta^2(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta)) + \frac{\alpha}{2} (\underline{\omega} \underline{e}^d) \bullet \underline{e}^d \\ &= \frac{\kappa}{2} \theta^2(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta)) + \frac{\alpha}{2} \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta(\mathbf{x})}} \underline{\omega} \left[\underline{e} - \frac{\theta(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta))}{3} \underline{x} \langle \xi \rangle \right]^2 dV_{\mathbf{x}'} \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

in which κ and α are two peridynamic parameters to be derived based on the energy conservation, and \underline{e}^d is the deviatoric part. Due to the new definition of dilatation scale-value function in Eq. (8), the new deviatoric part of the extension scalar state is expressed as

$$\underline{e}^d \langle \xi, \eta \rangle = \underline{e} \langle \xi \rangle - \frac{\theta(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta))}{3} \underline{x} \langle \xi \rangle \tag{15}$$

The classical strain energy density can be expressed in the following decomposed forms:

$$\mathcal{W}^c(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \begin{cases} \frac{k}{2} \text{tr}^2(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \mu \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^d : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^d & \text{for 3-D case} \\ \left[\frac{k}{2} + \frac{k^2}{4\mu} \right] \text{tr}^2(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \mu \sum_{i,j=1,2} \varepsilon_{ij}^d \varepsilon_{ij}^d & \text{for 2-D plane stress case} \\ \left[\frac{k}{2} + \frac{\mu}{9} \right] \text{tr}^2(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \mu \sum_{i,j=1,2} \varepsilon_{ij}^d \varepsilon_{ij}^d & \text{for 2-D plane strain case} \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

where k is the bulk modulus and μ is the shear modulus.

Based on the equivalence between classical strain energy density and peridynamic strain energy density in the pure distortion [44,66], the relations between peridynamic material parameter α and the classical shear modulus μ can be written in the following forms using the approximation $\underline{e}^d \approx \frac{\varepsilon_{ij}^d \xi_i \xi_j}{\|\xi\|}$ [67]

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \frac{15\mu}{m} & \text{for 3-D case} \\ \frac{8\mu}{m} & \text{for 2-D case} \end{cases} \tag{17}$$

For the pure isotropic dilatation, i.e., $\underline{e}^d = 0$, the macro-elastic energy density in peridynamics can be written as $\mathcal{W}^p(\xi, \eta) = \frac{1}{2} \kappa \theta^2(\underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta))$. Thus, the relations between peridynamic material parameter κ and the classical mechanical parameters can be written as [44,66,67]

$$\kappa = \begin{cases} k & \text{for 3-D case} \\ k + \frac{\mu}{9} \frac{(v+1)^2}{(2v-1)^2} & \text{for 2-D plane stress case} \\ k + \frac{\mu}{9} & \text{for 2-D plane strain case} \end{cases} \tag{18}$$

2.3. Decomposition of force states

The force scalar state for the ordinary and elastic materials can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{t}(\xi) &= 3\kappa\theta(\xi, \eta) \frac{\underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}(\xi)}{m} + \alpha \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{e}^d(\xi, \eta) \\ &= \left(\frac{3\kappa}{m} - \frac{\alpha}{3}\right) \theta(\xi, \eta) \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}(\xi) + \alpha \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{e}^d(\xi, \eta) \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

The peridynamic stress tensor at any material point \mathbf{x} can be expressed in the following form by the force vector state $\underline{\mathbf{T}}[\mathbf{x}, t](\xi)$.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x})} \underline{\mathbf{T}}(\xi) \otimes \underline{\mathbf{X}}(\xi) dV_{x'} \tag{20}$$

To describe the pure isotropic dilatation, the hydrostatic pressure scalar state $\underline{p}(\xi)$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{p}[\mathbf{x}, t](\xi) &= \frac{1}{3} \sigma_{mm} \delta_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{m=1,2,3} \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x})} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_m(\xi) \underline{\mathbf{X}}_m(\xi) dV_{x'} \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{m=1,2,3} \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x})} \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{\mathbf{M}}_m(\xi) \underline{\mathbf{X}}_m(\xi) dV_{x'} \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

The hydrostatic stress state $\underline{p}[\mathbf{x}, t](\xi)$ in 3-D cases can be recast as

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{p}[\mathbf{x}, t](\xi) &= \frac{1}{3} \left\{ \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x})} \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{x}(\xi) \sin[2](\psi) \cos[2](\phi) dV_{x'} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x})} \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{x}(\xi) \sin[2](\psi) \sin[2](\phi) dV_{x'} + \int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x})} \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{x}(\xi) \cos[2](\psi) dV_{x'} \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Considering $dV_{x'} = r^2 \sin(\psi) dr d\psi d\phi$, Eq. (22) equates to

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{p}[\mathbf{x}, t](\xi) &= \frac{1}{3} \left\{ \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi} \int_0^{\delta} \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{x}^3(\xi) \sin^3(\psi) \cos^2(\phi) d\underline{x}(\xi) d\psi d\phi \right. \\ &\quad + \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi} \int_0^{\delta} \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{x}^3(\xi) \sin^3(\psi) \sin^2(\phi) d\underline{x}(\xi) d\psi d\phi \\ &\quad \left. + \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi} \int_0^{\delta} \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{x}^3(\xi) \sin(\psi) \cos^2(\psi) d\underline{x}(\xi) d\psi d\phi \right\} \\ &= \frac{4\pi}{3} \int_0^{\delta} \underline{t}(\xi) \underline{x}^3(\xi) d\underline{x}(\xi) \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

According to [44], the isotropic part of force scalar state $\underline{t}^{iso}(\xi)$ is assumed as

$$\underline{t}^{iso}(\xi) = \beta \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}(\xi) \tag{24}$$

where β is the peridynamic stiffness parameter [45].

For the pure dilatation, it is assumed that only $\underline{t}^{iso}(\xi)$ contributes to the solid isotropic deformation. Substituting Eq. (24) into Eq. (23) and considering $m = 4\pi \int_0^{\delta} \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}^4(\xi) d\underline{x}(\xi)$, the isotropic part of force scalar state $\underline{t}^{iso}(\xi)$ can be written as

$$\underline{t}^{iso}(\xi) = \frac{3k}{m} \theta(\xi, \eta) \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}(\xi) \tag{25}$$

Thus, according to Eq. (19), the deviatoric part of force scalar state $\underline{t}^{dev}(\xi)$ can be expressed as

$$\underline{t}^{dev}(\xi) = \underline{t}(\xi) - \underline{t}^{iso}(\xi) = -5\mu\theta(\xi, \eta) \frac{\underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}(\xi)}{m} + \frac{15\mu}{m} \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{e}^d(\xi, \eta) \tag{26}$$

Similarly, for 2-D plane stress conditions, the isotropic and deviatoric parts of the force scalar vector states, i.e., $\underline{t}^{\text{iso}}(\xi)$ and $\underline{t}^{\text{dev}}(\xi)$, can be expressed as

$$\underline{t}^{\text{iso}}(\xi) = \frac{k}{m} \theta(\xi, \eta) \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}(\xi) \tag{27a}$$

$$\underline{t}^{\text{dev}}(\xi) = \frac{8\mu}{m} \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{e}(\xi, \eta) \tag{27b}$$

Moreover, these two parts for 2-D plane strain conditions are

$$\underline{t}^{\text{iso}}(\xi) = \frac{2k}{m} \theta(\xi, \eta) \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}(\xi) \tag{28a}$$

$$\underline{t}^{\text{dev}}(\xi) = -\frac{10\mu}{3} \theta(\xi, \eta) \frac{\underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{x}(\xi)}{m} + \frac{15\mu}{m} \underline{\omega}(\|\xi\|) \underline{e}(\xi, \eta) \tag{28b}$$

3. Bond-level energy-based failure criteria

The stored energy density in one given bond between two interacting material points within one *horizon* is expressed as [68,69]

$$\underline{w}(\xi) = \int_0^{\eta_{\text{final}}} \{ \underline{\mathbf{T}}[\mathbf{x}, t](\xi) - \underline{\mathbf{T}}[\mathbf{x}', t](\xi) \} \cdot d\eta \tag{29}$$

in which η_{final} is the relative displacement value at t_{final} .

Taking the properties of dual force density and elastic linearization into consideration [61,62], the simplified version of elastic strain energy density *scalar* state $\underline{w}(\xi)$ reads

$$\underline{w}(\xi) = \int_{\underline{\mathbf{X}}(\xi)}^{\underline{\mathbf{Y}}(\xi)} \underline{\mathbf{T}}[\mathbf{x}, t](\xi) \cdot d\underline{\mathbf{Y}}(\eta) = \frac{1}{2} \underline{t}(\xi) \cdot \underline{e}(\xi) \tag{30}$$

In this work, the stored elastic strain energy density *scalar* state $\underline{w}(\xi)$ is decomposed into the isotropic and deviatoric parts, i.e., $\underline{w}^{\text{iso}}(\xi)$ and $\underline{w}^{\text{dev}}(\xi)$.

$$\underline{w}(\xi) = \underline{w}^{\text{iso}}(\xi) + \underline{w}^{\text{dev}}(\xi) \tag{31}$$

Substituting Eqs. (9) and (15) into Eq. (30), and combining Eq. (31), the stored elastic strain energy density *scalar* state $\underline{w}(\xi)$ in a single bond ξ yields

$$\underline{w}(\xi) = \frac{1}{2} \underline{t}^{\text{iso}}(\xi) \cdot \underline{e}_n(\xi, \eta) + \frac{1}{2} \underline{t}^{\text{dev}}(\xi) \cdot \underline{e}^d(\xi, \eta) \tag{32}$$

Based on the conservation law, the critical fracture energy release rate due to the volumetric dilatation or deviatoric deformation can be obtained as

$$w_c^{\text{iso}} = \begin{cases} \frac{4\mathcal{G}_{Ic}}{\pi \delta^4} & \text{3-D cases} \\ \frac{9\mathcal{G}_{Ic}}{4\pi h \delta^3} & \text{2-D cases} \end{cases} \tag{33}$$

where h is the thickness and \mathcal{G}_{Ic} denotes the critical mode-I fracture energy release rate of solid materials.

Following the previous literatures [61,62], due to the pure shear deformation, the critical energy release rate can be obtained as

$$w_c^{\text{dev}} = \begin{cases} \frac{24\mathcal{G}_{IIc}}{\pi \delta^4} \sin^2(\phi) \cos^2(\phi) \sin^2(\vartheta) & \text{3-D cases} \\ \frac{45\mathcal{G}_{IIc}}{8\pi h \delta^3} \sin^2(\phi) \cos^2(\phi) & \text{2-D cases} \end{cases} \tag{34}$$

in which ϕ and ϑ are the direction angles of the bond ξ , and \mathcal{G}_{IIc} represents the critical mode-II fracture energy release rate of solids.

Fig. 3. The schematic illustration of mixed-mode fracture in brittle and quasi-brittle solids.

The Benzeggagh-Kenane Semi-empirical failure criterion provides a unified framework for capturing pure tensile fracture, pure shear fracture, and mixed-mode tension-shear fracture in brittle and quasi-brittle solids.

$$G_c = G_{Ic} + (G_{IIc} - G_{Ic}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right)^\gamma \tag{35}$$

where G_c is the critical mixed-mode fracture energy release rate, G_I and G_{II} are the mode-I and mode-II fracture energy release rates, and γ represents the empirical material parameters.

Referring to the applications of Benzeggagh–Kenane Semi-empirical failure criterion in phase-field modeling [19] and peridynamic interface delamination failure analysis on composite materials [62], the new bond-level energy-based failure criterion is employed to simulate the mixed-mode failure phenomena in brittle and quasi-brittle solids, which is stated as follows

$$\underline{w}(\xi) \geq \min \left\{ w_c^{iso}, w_c^{dev}, w_c^{iso} + (w_c^{dev} - w_c^{iso}) \left(\frac{\underline{w}^{dev}(\xi)}{\underline{w}^{iso}(\xi) + \underline{w}^{dev}(\xi)} \right)^\gamma \right\} \tag{36}$$

When the new bond-level energy-based failure criterion in Eq. (36) reaches, the bond ξ is broken. The scalar function of a bond state in the brittle solids can be then written as

$$g(\xi, t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{Eq. (36) is satisfied} \\ 0 & \text{Eq. (36) is not satisfied} \end{cases} \tag{37}$$

To describe the strain softening behavior of quasi-brittle solids, we employ a general scale function $g(\xi, t)$ to describe the damage softening behavior of one bond in the post-failure regime, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 3. Yang et al. [60] summarized linear, exponential, bilinear and trilinear different softening laws in the form of bond stretch. In this work, we adopt the simplest one, i.e., linear softening law, to describe the strain softening behavior of quasi-brittle solid materials.

$$g(\xi, t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \underline{w}(\xi) < w_{ini} \\ 1 - \frac{\underline{w}(\xi) - w_{ini}}{w_f - w_{ini}} & w_{ini} \leq \underline{w}(\xi) < w_f \\ 0 & \underline{w}(\xi) \geq w_f \end{cases} \tag{38}$$

where w_{ini} is the bond-level energy density determined based on the Benzeggagh–Kenane Semi-empirical failure criterion, which can be numerically determined in simulations according to Eq. (36). w_f denotes the ultimate value of bond-level energy density, where $\underline{w}(\xi) \geq w_f$ indicates that interaction via this bond vanishes.

For the geomaterials, e.g., soils and rocks, the non-linear shear energy yield criterion [70,71] is employed at the bond level to realize the failure analysis. The critical bond-level energy density can be expressed as

$$w_c(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\xi}, t) = \frac{1}{2G} \left(\frac{\sigma_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t) - \sigma_3(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t)}{2 \cos \varphi} + \frac{\sigma_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t) + \sigma_3(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t)}{2} \tan \varphi \right)^2 - \frac{c^2}{2G} \tag{39}$$

in which $\sigma_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t)$ and $\sigma_3(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t)$ are the maximum and minimum principal stresses on one bond, which can be calculated based on Eq. (20). φ and c are the internal friction angle and cohesion strength, indicating the Mohr–Coulomb criterion as a special case.

In this special case, the scalar function of a bond state in Eq. (37) is rewritten as

$$g(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t) = \begin{cases} 1 & w_c(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\xi}, t) < 0 \\ 0 & w_c(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\xi}, t) \geq 0 \end{cases} \tag{40}$$

It is noted that the critical bond-level energy density $w_c(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\xi}, t)$ is determined based on the deformation and stress states at each time step. And w_c^{iso} in Eq. (33) is also used to determine the pure mode-I fracture in geomaterials. This computing paradigm is a general strategy related to other energy-based failure criteria.

Following the original nonlocal idea [22,23], the damage variable at any material points \mathbf{x} reads

$$d(\mathbf{x}, t) = 1 - \frac{\int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x})} g(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t) dV_{\mathbf{x}'}}{\int_{\mathcal{H}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x})} dV_{\mathbf{x}'}} \tag{41}$$

4. Numerical solution strategy

In this work, we use the adaptive dynamic relaxation (ADR) method [72] to obtain stable quasi-static solutions. The explicit form of the numerical solution strategy is employed. We utilize the typical influence function $\omega(|\boldsymbol{\xi}|) = \frac{|\boldsymbol{\xi}|}{\delta}$ in the following numerical examples. The computational domain is discretized into material points with a uniform distribution in numerical simulations. The governing equation of motion at material point \mathbf{x}_i can be expressed as

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}_i) \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}_i, t) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{H}_{\mathbf{x}_i}}^{\mathcal{N}} [\mathbf{T}[\mathbf{x}_i, t] \langle \boldsymbol{\xi}_{ij} \rangle - \mathbf{T}[\mathbf{x}_j, t] \langle \boldsymbol{\xi}_{ji} \rangle] V_j + \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}_i, t) \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{N} \tag{42}$$

where \mathbf{x}_i is the material point and \mathbf{x}_j is the neighbor material point within $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbf{x}_i}$, \mathcal{M} is the total number of neighboring material points around \mathbf{x}_i , and \mathcal{N} represents the total number of material points in computational domain. The explicit time integration strategy are used to obtain the displacement, velocity and acceleration at each material point at time t .

To obtain the stable solutions under the static and quasi-static conditions, the governing equation of motion, i.e., can be written in the following form by introducing the fictitious inertia and damping coefficients.

$$\mathbf{A} \ddot{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{X}, t) + c \mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{X}, t) = \mathcal{L}_u(\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{U}', \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}') \tag{43}$$

in which \mathbf{A} is the fictitious diagonal density matrix, c is the adaptive damping coefficient determined based on the lowest frequency of computational system using Rayleigh’s quotient. \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{U} are the positions and displacement fields of all material points in the computational domain, and \mathcal{L}_u is the summation of internal and external forces. In the numerical simulation, \mathbf{U} and c can be calculated by the following iterative procedure. In addition, the determination of \mathbf{A} can be referred to [54,72].

$$\dot{\mathbf{U}}^{n+1/2} = \frac{[(2 - c^n \Delta t) \dot{\mathbf{U}}^{n-1/2} + 2 \Delta t \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathcal{L}_u^n]}{2 + c^n \Delta t} \tag{44}$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{n+1} = \mathbf{U}^{n+1} + \Delta t \dot{\mathbf{U}}^{n+1/2} \tag{45}$$

$$c^{n+1} = 2 \sqrt{\frac{(\mathbf{U}^{n+1})^T [(\mathcal{L}_u^n - \mathcal{L}_u^{n+1}) \mathbf{A}^{-1} / (\Delta t \dot{\mathbf{U}}^{n+1/2})] \mathbf{U}^{n+1}}{[(\mathbf{U}^{n+1})^T \mathbf{U}^{n+1}]}} \tag{46}$$

Fig. 4. (a) Layout of the semi-circular bending beam; and (b) numerical sample composed of peridynamic material points.

in which n is the n th iteration. The unknown velocity field at $t^{-1/2}$ and initial value of damping coefficient c^1 are assumed as

$$\dot{\mathbf{U}}^{1/2} = \frac{\Delta t \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathcal{L}_u^0}{2} \tag{47}$$

$$c^1 = 0 \tag{48}$$

5. Benchmark problems

We validate our numerical model by two numerical examples: (i) semi-circular bending tests on rock-like materials, and (ii) mixed tension-shear double-edge notched tests on concrete. In the first numerical example, we utilize the bond-level Mohr–Coulomb failure criterion to simulate the crack initiation and propagation process. In the second numerical example, we employ the bond-level Benzeggagh–Kenane Semi-empirical failure criterion to predict the mixed-mode fracture in concrete.

5.1. Example-I: Semi-circular bend tests

Polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) is widely recognized as a rock-like material for conducting fracture tests [73]. In this study, we used our new peridynamic model to simulate several semi-circular bend (SCB) specimens for mixed-mode fracture tests on PMMA. Each SCB specimen is a semi-circle with a radius of $R = 50.0$ mm and features an edged crack with a length of $a = 0.3R = 15.0$ mm and inclination angle α . The semi-circular rock-like specimen is supported on two bottom supports, with a distance of $2S$ (i.e., $S/R = 0.43$), and is subjected to prescribed vertical movement, i.e., \dot{u}_y , as illustrated in Fig. 4(a). To demonstrate the capabilities of our proposed model, we conducted six numerical tests with different inclination angles, specifically $\alpha = 0^\circ$, $\alpha = 10^\circ$, $\alpha = 20^\circ$, $\alpha = 30^\circ$, $\alpha = 40^\circ$, and $\alpha = 50^\circ$.

The numerical simulations of SCB specimens considered in this study are plane-strain cases. The mechanical parameters for the PMMA SCB specimens used in the simulations are based on literature values and assumed to be as follows: Young’s modulus $E = 3.75$ GPa, Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.35$, material density $\rho = 1,410.0$ kg/m³ [74], cohesion strength $c = 2.74$ MPa, friction angle $\tan \varphi = 1.7$, and uniaxial tensile strength $f_t = 10.0$ MPa [75]. The computational domain is discretized using 15,714 material points with a uniform spacing of $\Delta x = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ m, as shown in Fig. 4(b). We postulate the horizon δ to be $\delta = 4.015\Delta x$, resulting in a nonlocal internal length scale of 2.0×10^{-3} m. To simulate the constraints and loading conditions, we apply all constraints on the bottom and loading on the top to areas of $4\Delta x \times 4\Delta x$, as illustrated in Fig. 4. For all simulations, the loading condition at the top of the SCB specimens is $\dot{u}_y = -0.005$ mm/min.

Fig. 5(a) displays the predicted crack growth paths, and Fig. 5(b) shows the calculated maximum principal stress fields in the numerical sample with $\alpha = 0^\circ$. We observe that the crack initiates at the tip of the preexisting edged notch and then propagates along the loading direction. The concentration of maximum principal stress σ_1 , as demonstrated in Figs. 5(a)–(b), drives the crack initiation and propagation, indicating final tension-dominated

Fig. 5. Numerical results of the rock semi-circular bending tests: (a) peridynamic predictions of crack growth paths; (b) maximum principal stress evolution (unit: Pa); (c) mechanical response of axial load versus axial displacement curve, and (d) comparison with the reported experimental observation [73] and phase-field simulation [76].

failure. Fig. 5(c) shows the axial load versus axial displacement curve for the simulated sample. Four representative points associated with the snapshots shown in Figs. 5(a)–(b) are labeled in the mechanical response displayed in Fig. 5(c). The crack initiates around the point of peak axial load, and crack propagation occurs in the post-failure regime.

Finally, we compare the predicted ultimate failure pattern by our peridynamic model with those obtained from laboratory tests [73] and phase-field simulations [76], as depicted in Fig. 5(d). This comparison demonstrates that our current predicted crack propagation pattern agrees well with both laboratory observations and phase-field simulations, indicating the effectiveness of our model.

To showcase the ability of our model to predict mixed-mode fracture phenomena, we proceed to simulate an additional five SCB rock-like samples with various inclination angles (α) in plane-strain conditions. We vary α from 10° to 50° in increments of 10° . Fig. 6(a) displays the five initial configurations, as well as the resulting crack propagation patterns, and compares them against experimental observations. During SCB testing simulations, the mixed-mode cracks initiate from the notch tips and propagate towards the loading region. The agreement between the predicted crack propagation patterns and experimental observations demonstrates the qualitative correctness of our model.

In Fig. 6(b), we present the macro-mechanical axial load versus axial displacement curves for the six simulations. It can be observed that as α increases, the peak values of axial loads also increase. Furthermore, the crack initiation loads from the six numerical tests are summarized in Fig. 6(c) and compared with the laboratory testing data [73]. The results show that the numerical predicted values are in good agreement with the experimental data, indicating the quantitative accuracy of our model.

5.2. Example-II: Mixed tension-shear double-edge notched tests

To further demonstrate the ability of the proposed model to predict mixed-mode fractures, we consider the double-edge-notched concrete specimen subjected to combined shear and tension loads in the Nooru-Mohamed test [77,78]. Fig. 7(a) illustrates the geometric configuration and detailed dimensions. The top and left boundaries experience horizontal and vertical displacements at equal rates of $\dot{u}_x = \dot{u}_y = 10^{-3}$ mm/s. Meanwhile, the displacement fields on the bottom and right boundaries are constrained, as shown in Fig. 7(a). We use the bond-level Benzeggagh-Kenane failure criterion and adopt the following mechanical parameters [79]: Young’s modulus $E = 32.0$ GPa, Poisson’s

Fig. 6. Effect of notch inclined angle α on (a) the predicted crack growth paths against experimental observations [73], (b) mechanical responses of $F_a \sim u_a$ curves and (c) crack initiation loads against laboratory testing data [73].

Fig. 7. (a) layout of a double-edge notched concrete specimen with unit of mm; (b) snapshots of crack growth paths; (c) maximum principal stress evolution (unit: Pa); (d) maximum shear stress evolution (unit: Pa); (e) strain energy density evolution (unit: J); and comparison of crack trajectories with experimental observations [77,78].

ratio $\nu = 0.2$, mode-I fracture energy release rate $\mathcal{G}_{Ic} = 0.1$ N/mm, and mode-II fracture energy release rate $\mathcal{G}_{IIc} = 20\mathcal{G}_{Ic}$. We assume the empirical parameter in the Benzeggagh-Kenane failure criterion is $\gamma = 2.6$ [19]. Moreover, $\Delta x = 1.0$ mm and $\delta = 4.0$ mm are employed in this simulation.

The representative snapshots of crack growth paths d , maximum principal stress σ_1 , maximum shear stress τ_{\max} , and strain energy density are displayed in Figs. 7(b)–(e). Our observations suggest that the concentration of σ_1 and τ_{\max} drives the initiation and propagation of mixed-mode cracks. We compare our numerically predicted crack growth paths with laboratory experimental observations [77,78] in Fig. 7(f). The good agreement on mixed-mode crack growth paths highlights the effectiveness and qualitative accuracy of our model.

Fig. 8 compares the vertical force versus vertical displacement curve for the simulated double-edge notched concrete specimen under mixed tension-shear loading with laboratory testing data [77,78]. We can find that our numerical results are close to the laboratory testing data. This comparison highlights the quantitative capabilities

Fig. 8. Comparison of the calculated mechanical response, i.e., vertical force versus displacement curve, with the laboratory testing data [77,78].

of the proposed bond-level energy-based peridynamic model and further verifies its validation under complex mixed-mode loading.

6. Numerical simulations

The objective of this section is to examine the mixed-mode fracture phenomena in rock-like materials by utilizing our proposed bond-level energy-based peridynamic model. To achieve this, we reproduce some uniaxial compression tests on fissured gypsum specimens and compare the numerical results with reported experiments [80–82] and phase-field simulations [19,83–85]. Our study focuses on three types of fissured gypsum samples: (i) single fissure, (ii) two parallel collinear fissures, and (iii) double echelon fissures. In this study, all numerical simulations are assumed as the plane-strain conditions, and the bond-level energy-based Mohr–Coulomb failure criterion is used. Referring to [81,84], the mechanical parameters of gypsum are summarized as follows: bulk modulus $K = 2.84$ GPa, shear modulus $G = 2.59$ GPa, uniaxial tension strength $f_t = 3.2$ MPa, cohesion strength $c = 10.7$ MPa, and friction angle $\varphi = 28^\circ$.

6.1. Crack initiation and propagation process

To commence, we simulate the crack initiation and propagation process of a fissured rock-like sample in the uniaxial compression test. This process is schematically illustrated in Fig. 9(a). The fissured gypsum sample features a single inclined preexisting fissure with dimensions of length $2a = 12.7$ mm, width 1.27 mm, and inclined angle $\alpha = 45^\circ$ with respect to the horizontal direction. Additionally, the rock-like sample has dimensions of length $L = 76.0$ mm and height $H = 152.0$ mm. The prescribed displacement field \bar{u}_y is applied on the top boundary and the fixed displacement field $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$ is employed on the bottom boundary. The simulation proceeds under displacement control with each displacement increment of $\Delta\bar{u}_y = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mm.

A total of 184,832 material points are used to discretize the computational domain with the preexisting fissure by initial damage variable d , as shown in Fig. 9(b). The material point spacing used for discretization is $\Delta = 0.25$ mm, and the simulation adopts a horizon δ of 1.0 mm. The horizon δ is similar to the internal length scale in the phase-field approach, and it is estimated based on the thickness of fracture process zone observed from laboratory experiments. It is typically 2 to 15 times larger than the rock grain size.

Fig. 10 presents the calculated crack initiation and propagation process of the rock-like specimens studied in [80,81]. We can observe that our numerical simulation well reproduces the real cracking evolution process. When $\bar{u}_y = 0.175$ mm, wing cracks are firstly initiated from tips of the preexisting fissure (see Fig. 10a). When \bar{u}_y increases from 0.175 mm to 0.550 mm, wing cracks first propagate perpendicular to the preexisting fissure, and subsequently along the direction of maximum principal stress (see Figs. 10b–c). As \bar{u}_y continues to increase,

Fig. 9. (a) Geometric and boundary conditions of a fissured rock-like sample in the uniaxial compression; and (b) peridynamic sample with damage distribution in computational domain.

Fig. 10. The failure process of fissured rock-like specimen containing one single preexisting crack subjected to the uniaxial compressive loads.

Fig. 11. Comparison of (a)–(b) the simulated crack propagation pattern by our peridynamics with (c)–(d) laboratory experimental observations [81,82].

wing cracks also continue to propagate, while secondary cracks are initiated from the preexisting fissure tips (see Fig. 10d). Then, secondary cracks propagate along the direction of the preexisting fissure, and the horsetail cracks happens (see Figs. 10e–f).

Fig. 11 compares the ultimate crack propagation patterns obtained from our peridynamic simulation with those from previous laboratory experiments [81,82]. Our simulated crack growth paths (see Figs. 11a–b) agree well with the observations from laboratory testing (see Figs. 11c–d). In the representative snapshots of this simulation, the evolution of the maximum principal stress σ_1 and maximum shear stress τ_{max} are shown in Figs. 12a and 12b, respectively. Our analysis reveals that the concentration of σ_1 drives the initiation and propagation of wing cracks (Fig. 12a), while the concentration of τ_{max} leads to the formation and propagation of secondary cracks (Fig. 12b). Moreover, we find that the horsetail cracks consist of both secondary shear and tensile cracks, as shown in Figs. 11–12.

Remark. The horsetail cracks found in rocks are considered to be mixed-mode fractures, consisting of both tensile and secondary shear cracks. The recently developed bond-level energy-based peridynamic model allows for a clear differentiation between these two types of cracks, similar to the mixed-mode fracture phenomena captured by the phase-field approach [83,84]. The numerical results of the horsetail crack propagation under mixed-mode loading conditions emphasize the significance of distinct fracture mechanisms.

Fig. 13 compares the axial stress–axial strain curve of the simulated gypsum sample with quasi-static simulations by Fei and Choo [84] and experimental observations in the laboratory [80]. Both simulations use the plane-strain hypothesis, making this comparison meaningful. Fig. 13 shows $\sigma_a \sim \epsilon_a$ with four representative points labeled corresponding to the snapshots shown in Fig. 12. Both simulations predict similar mechanical responses with comparable peak strengths in the pre-peak regime, which are close to the laboratory testing data. Compared to the phase-field simulation [84], the current simulation predicts a more pronounced stress drop in the post-peak regime. The good agreement on crack propagation patterns and mechanical responses further indicates the effectiveness and correctness of our model in predicting mixed-mode fracture phenomena in rocks.

6.2. Crack propagation and coalescence process

To study the capabilities of bond-level energy-based peridynamic model for simulating crack propagation and coalescence in rock-like materials, we simulate a rock-like sample containing two parallel collinear preexisting

Fig. 12. Numerical results of (a) the maximum principal stress σ_1 and (b) the maximum shear stress τ_{max} during the progressive failure process in the uniaxial compression.

Fig. 13. Comparison of the current predicted mechanical responses, i.e., $\sigma_a \sim \epsilon_a$, against with phase-field simulations [84] and laboratory testing data [80].

fissures in the uniaxial compression test. The rock-like material is gypsum, whose mechanical parameters have been stated in the above numerical example.

The geometric, boundary and loading conditions are plotted in Fig. 14(a), which are the same as those reported. The inclination angles of two fissures are the same as $\alpha = 45^\circ$, and rock bridge ligament length $c = a = 6.35$ mm. In the numerical sample, a total of 103,968 material points are employed with $\Delta = 0.25$ mm and δ of 1.0 mm. Fig. 14(b) displays the initial configuration of a numerical sample with the distribution of d for the two preexisting fissures.

Fig. 15 illustrates the crack initiation, propagation, and coalescence process in the uniaxial compression test. The results reveal that wing cracks are first initiated from the tips of preexisting fissures when \bar{u}_y reaches 0.350 mm (as depicted in Fig. 15a). As \bar{u}_y increases to 0.595 mm (shown in Fig. 15a-c), wing cracks initially propagate perpendicular to the preexisting fissures and then follow the direction of σ_1 . As the deformation continues (as seen in Fig. 15d-e), secondary cracks are initiated from the tips of preexisting fissures and propagate towards each other, resulting in the coalescence of secondary cracks and tensile cracks in the rock bridge region, as shown in Fig. 15(e).

Fig. 14. (a) Geometric and boundary conditions of a fissured rock-like sample containing two parallel collinear preexisting fissures in the uniaxial compression; and (b) peridynamic sample with damage distribution in computational domain at the initial state.

Fig. 15. Numerical results of crack propagation and coalescence process of a fissured rock specimen subjected to the uniaxial compression.

Fig. 16 shows a comparison of the crack coalescence pattern simulated by our peridynamics approach with previous phase-field simulations [84] and laboratory experiments [81]. Our peridynamics simulation results and the phase-field predictions both demonstrate good agreement with the experimental observations. Moreover, we observed that the propagation and coalescence of cracks in the rock bridge zone impede the propagation of wing cracks initiated from the inner tips.

Fig. 17(a) and Fig. 17(b) present four representative snapshots of our simulation, showcasing the evolution of the maximum principal stress σ_1 and maximum shear stress τ_{max} , respectively. From these figures, we can observe that the concentrations of σ_1 and τ_{max} drive the initiation and propagation of wing cracks and secondary cracks, respectively. Furthermore, our stress evolution analysis indicates that the crack coalescence pattern in the rock bridge region is formed by secondary shear cracks and tensile cracks. Thus, crack coalescence pattern observed in this rock-like sample can be classified as the mixed-mode tension-shear one.

During crack propagation and coalescence process, we denote four representative snapshots in Fig. 17 on the $\sigma_a \sim \epsilon_a$ curve shown in Fig. 18. We observe that the crack initiation and propagation occur in the pre-peak regime, while crack coalescence happens in the post-peak regime, accompanied with the stress drop.

To demonstrate the robustness of our model, we study the numerical convergence on crack propagation and coalescence in rock-like materials. In peridynamic framework, δ -convergence, i.e., a fixed nonlocal ratio $m = \delta/\Delta x$ and changing δ , is regarded as a standard to examine the robustness of predicting crack propagation and coalescence patterns [43]. So, we carry out numerical simulations of four sane fissured gypsum samples (see Fig. 14), i.e., Sample-I \sim Sample-IV, with different material point discretization (see Table 1).

The crack propagation and coalescence patterns of four numerical samples are plotted in Fig. 19. The crack types, crack growth paths and crack coalescence modes in these four gypsum samples are close to each other. For the fixed m , as horizon δ decreases, the mixed tension-shear crack coalescence mode become more apparent. The associated

Fig. 16. Comparison of crack coalescence pattern predicted by (a) our peridynamics with (b) phase-field simulation [84] and (c) laboratory experimental observation [81].

Fig. 17. Crack propagation and coalescence process: snapshots of spatio-temporal distributions of (a) maximum principal stress (unit: Pa) and (b) maximum shear stress (unit: Pa).

Table 1

Material point distributions in computational domain for numerical convergence study.

Computational parameters	Sample-I	Sample-II	Sample-III	Sample-IV
Nonlocal ratio $m = \delta/\Delta x$	4	4	4	4
Horizon δ (mm)	2.0	1.6	1.32	1.0
Point space Δx (mm)	0.5	0.4	0.33	0.25
Number of points	46,208	72,200	103,968	184,832

mechanical responses are depicted in Fig. 20. We observe that the numerical prediction of mechanical responses, i.e., $\sigma_a \sim \varepsilon_a$ curves, in four samples are also similar to one another, while we find from Fig. 20 a slight increase in the calculated peak stress as δ decreases. These comparisons further demonstrate the numerical convergence of our new peridynamic model for simulating crack propagation and coalescence in rock and rock-like materials.

6.3. Discussions

To further demonstrate the capabilities of our model for modeling the mixed-mode fracture process, we simulate a series of gypsum samples containing double echelon fissures, which have been experimentally reported in [81,82]. The geometric, loading and boundary conditions are shown in Fig. 21. Two parallel double echelon fissures have

Fig. 18. Mechanical responses of crack propagation and coalescence process, i.e., axial stress versus axial strain curve with four representative points, in the uniaxial compression test.

Fig. 19. δ -convergence study on crack propagation and coalescence patterns.

the same length of $2a = 12.7$ mm and aperture of 1.27 mm. The initial arrangement of double echelon fissures are described by a inclination angle α , a fissure spacing w , and a continuity c , as displayed in Fig. 21. The terminology “ $\alpha - w - c$ ” is used to represent numerical samples with different fissure configurations, referring to [83,84].

In this work, we focus on numerical samples with two various inclination angles, i.e., $\alpha = 30^\circ$ and $\alpha = 45^\circ$, and two different w , i.e., $w = a$ and $w = 2a$. The simulated crack coalescence patterns of four different numerical samples are displayed in Fig. 22. For the sample with $30^\circ - a - 2a$, crack coalescence pattern in rock bridge are caused by the secondary shear cracks, belonging to the shear crack coalescence mode, as shown in Fig. 22(a). For the samples with $45^\circ - a - 2a$ and $30^\circ - 2a - 2a$, we observe from Figs. 22(b)–(c) that the interaction among

Fig. 20. δ -convergence study on the axial stress–axial strain curves of four gypsum samples in uniaxial compression tests.

Fig. 21. Geometric and boundary conditions of rock specimens containing double echelon fissures, where the ligament length s is the distance between two inner fissure tips.

secondary shear cracks and out-of-plane tensile cracks results in the ultimate mixed tension-shear crack coalescence mode. The mixed tension-shear crack coalescence mode presents a zig-zag coalescence pattern, which is similar to the reported experimental observations [81] and phase-field simulations [84]. While, the internal wing crack coalesces with secondary shear crack in the sample with $45^\circ - 2a - 2a$, leading to the final mixed tension-shear coalescence mode, as seen in Fig. 22(d).

To quantitatively analyze the crack coalescence stress in our simulations, we compare our results with those obtained in laboratory experiments [81] and phase-field simulations [83]. Fig. 23 presents the comparison. We find that the peridynamic results agree well with both the experimental data and phase-field modeling results, indicating that our model can well capture the variation trend observed in the laboratory experiments.

These numerical results demonstrate that the proposed bond-level energy-based peridynamic model can well capture both mixed-mode fracture phenomena in individual cases and complex transition of crack coalescence patterns in different figure configurations, qualitatively and quantitatively. Furthermore, our numerical approach also has the capabilities of providing deeply physical insights into mixed-mode fracture mechanisms in rocks.

Fig. 22. Crack coalescence patterns of four fissured rock specimens with different types of preexisting fissures ($\alpha - w - c$): (a) $30^\circ - a - 2a$; (b) $45^\circ - a - 2a$; (c) $30^\circ - 2a - 2a$; (d) $45^\circ - 2a - 2a$.

Fig. 23. Comparison of simulated crack coalescence stress in rock specimens with double echelon fissures with experimental observation [81] and phase-field simulations [83].

7. Closure

In this work, we develop a novel bond-level energy-based peridynamic formulation to model the mixed-mode fracture in rocks. Our model includes several new features, such as a dilatation scale function that distinguishes between volumetric and deviatoric deformations, the force-state decomposition, and a computational strategy to bridge the gap between bond-level energy-based failure criterion and specific macro-mechanical failure criteria for brittle and quasi-brittle solids. To test our model, we use the Benzeggagh-Kenane semi-empirical failure criterion

for concretes and a non-linear shear energy yield criterion for rock/rock-like materials. We validate our model by presenting two benchmark problems: the semi-circular bend tests of rocks and double-edge-notched concrete specimens under mixed tension-shear loading. We also demonstrate the effectiveness and robustness of our model by simulating a series of fissured rock-like samples in uniaxial compression tests. We investigate the effects of fissure inclination angle, fissure spacing, fissure configuration, and nonlocal characteristic length on the numerically predicted crack growth paths and crack coalescence patterns. Work is underway to incorporate the effects of anisotropy and crack surface friction on fracture behavior in geological media.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yunteng Wang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Figures, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Review & editing. **Wei Wu:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

Authors declare that there are no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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